

Management of Diabetic Foot Ulcer

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Background

- Diabetes was the 7th leading cause of death in the U.S. in 2015
- Accounted for deaths of 30.3 million Americans
- In 2015, rates of diagnosed diabetes increased with age:
 - 4% among ages 18-44 years old
 - 17% in ages 46-64 years old
 - 25% among 65 years and older
- Associated acute and long-term complications of diabetes include:
 - Premature death
 - Stroke
 - Heart disease
 - Blindness
 - Kidney disease
 - Amputations of toes, feet, or lower extremities
- Prevalent among U.S. veterans due to high incidence of obesity in this population
 - Affects nearly 25% of patients

Problem

- No universal practice guidelines addressing the complication of diabetic foot ulcer (DFU)
- Evidence-based clinical practice guideline (CPG) is needed for management of diabetes with an associated DFU

Purpose

Adapt, implement, and evaluate an evidence-based CPG to improve the management of DFUs in elderly veterans

Methods

- Project procedure approved by CSUF IRB, supported by project site
- 75-bed transitional, inpatient care unit
- October 2019 to January 2020
- Johns Hopkins Quality and Safety Research Group model

Supporting Framework

Results

- Of 141 patients screened, 10 patients were identified with DFUs
- Wound care orders appropriately tailored based on the presenting status of wound, wound changes, or healing
- Assessment of ischemia, infection, and neuropathy were performed ($n=9$)
- Appropriate referral to orthopedic, vascular, or podiatry ($n=10$)
- $A1c \leq 7$ ($n=4$), $A1c \geq 7$ ($n=6$)
- Complete wound healing not observed on this limited project

Discussion

- CPG effectively implemented for patients identified with DFUs
- A simple and easy-to-follow CPG algorithm facilitated implementation and enhanced adherence
- Characteristic of the DFUs on presentation determines status of the ulcer and its potential associated complications (i.e., infection with or without surgical intervention)
- Osteomyelitis almost always results from an extension of infection from a chronic ulcer as complications involving foot and ankle

Implications

- Critical element of effective treatment and management involves nursing
- Nurses' roles are vital in assessing for appropriate therapy and providing timely interventions
- Patient education, thorough skin or wound assessment, and collaborative team approach promote better patient outcomes and potential cost containment
- Knowledge of current EBP is crucial in the effective management of DFUs for wound healing and prevention of complications
- Further research is needed to evaluate long-term impact of consistent, evidence-based standard of care for patients with DFU

Conclusions

- Diabetes-related foot complication is identified as the single most common cause of morbidity among patients with diabetes
- Underlying PVD and PN diminishes DFU symptoms until the evidence of non-healing ulcers become evident
- Prudent health care clinicians must consistently follow evidence-based CPG for improvement of patients overall long-term outcomes